

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION” International Conference on Teacher Education

USING WIKI-TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation. We know that using technologies in teaching English is absolutely vital during the lesson in Uzbekistan. This article presents a theoretical and methodological model of application wiki technologies for the development of written and speech skills of non-linguistic student's university issues related to the relationship of participants are considered educational process in the conditions of informatization of education; this article discusses some problems in using wiki technologies at school and universities; and their solutions to problems.

Key words: wiki-technology, theory, language, practice, activity, wiki glossary, methods, wiki essay, project, assessment, feedback

Annotatsiya. Biz bilamizki, O'zbekistonda ingliz tilini o'qitishda texnologiyalardan foydalanish juda muhim hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada nolingvistik universitet talabalarining yozma va nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun wiki-texnologiyalarini qo'llashning nazariy va uslubiy modeli taqdim etilgan; ushbu maqolada maktab va universitetlarda wiki-texnologiyalardan foydalanishdagi ba'zi muammolar va muammolarni hal qilish usullari muhokama qilinadi.

This article presents a theoretical and methodological model of wiki-technologies for the development of writing skills of non-linguistic university students' issues related to the relationship of participants are considered educational process in the conditions of informatization of education; didactic potential of organizing the learning process in writing and speech activities based on wiki technology; ways to integrate wiki technology into foreign language teaching; a format for three tasks has been developed: a wiki glossary, joint wiki essay, wiki project with elements of self and mutual assessment; considered ways to implement interactivity, assessment and feedback based on the proposed tasks; possible difficulties of joint work on a wiki site and conditions for effective integration of wiki technology into the process of teaching a foreign language; motivational factor of learning revealed on the wiki site.

Traditionally, in a non-linguistic university, teaching the discipline “Foreign Language” is not given due attention, and this is especially true for the formation and developing the ability to express one's thoughts in writing. "And if learning to read, primarily of specialized literature, has strong traditions dating back to Soviet times, and teaching listening and speaking was established in post-reconstruction times during the transition to communication methods teaching foreign languages, then the situation with writing, as a rule, is no matter. [1, p. 46].

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However, in the modern world, science student's faculties must be capable of written communication and own educational standards of Moscow State University named after M.V. Lomonosov from 2011 year [3], the requirements for mastering instrumental competencies (IK-2), and the task has been set to graduate all students, including number of non-linguistic faculties, with a level of foreign language proficiency not lower than level B2 according to the Pan-European CEFR scale [2]. This contradiction can be overcome if we propose a new model for the development of foreign language written and speech skills, based on the use of modern information and communication technologies, for example the social service wiki.

The modeling procedure has found wide application in pedagogy. At with the help of modeling, you can predict actions and events in the system, i.e. V case with pedagogical modeling to determine the course of educational process under certain conditions. According to V.P. Zagvyazinsky, modeling is characterized by the systematic formation of two spaces: material (words, combinations, text), i.e. real creation processes, the relationship between knowledge and the ideal (scheme), which is the result of the mapping real object, process, phenomenon" [4, p. 66].

Models can be used either as a research technique to study, explain and clarify the pedagogical object under study, or as a tool to influence the construction and functioning of the studied pedagogical object on the basis of the conducted model representations [2, p. 139]. In order for the model to be functional, it must meet the following requirements: a) simplicity; b) inherence, i.e. the ability of the created model and environment to adapt to each other; V) adequacy, i.e. the ability of the model to provide the ability to achieve the intended goal in accordance with the criteria. Thus, the connection between the model and the subject is determined (through compliance with the first requirement), with environment (through compliance with the second requirement) and with the simulated object (through compliance with the third requirement) [1, p. 275-278].

Let us turn to reference literature to clarify the concept of model. The most concise explanation is given by the Concise Dictionary of Pedagogical concepts in which a model is described as a diagram of some phenomenon, representing it in general form" [2, p. 81].

In the Terminological Dictionary-Directory of Psychological and Pedagogical disciplines, the teaching model is considered as a systematized a complex of basic patterns of organizing the activities of the student and teacher during the implementation of training" [3, p. 53]. According to E.G. Azimov and A.N. Shchukin,

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the teaching model is individual interpretation by the teacher in the classroom of the teaching method in relation to specific goals and working conditions" [1, p. 145-146].

Summarizing the above, it seems appropriate to define the concept of learning model in a way: a learning model is a system of interactions between participants in the educational process, technologies used and means of teaching in accordance with specific goals, pedagogical objectives and learning conditions within the framework of the selected approaches and methods training.

Within the framework of this study, a particular methodological model can be described as follows: model of teaching written and speech activities students of non-linguistic universities within the framework of blended learning based on wiki technology is a system of interactions between the teacher and students in the information and educational environment of the wiki site using interactive problem-oriented group assignments and technology mutual assessment to optimize the development of foreign language written and speech skills taking into account the professional orientation of students.

The proposed model includes target, theoretical, technological and evaluative and performance blocks. The target block defines the purpose and content training students of non-linguistic universities in written and speech skills in accordance with the requirements for the formation of competencies of the modern Federal State Educational Standard for Higher Education in direction "Biological Sciences", the social order of society associated with society's need for competent natural science graduate's faculties, able to use written and verbal skills to establish professional connections, and the existing contradictions between the need for informatization of education and insufficient development of methods teaching written and speech skills in a foreign language at a non-linguistic university based on CT.

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